

Table S1. LAP and LAP sodium salt pharmacokinetic parameters determined by non-compartmental and compartmental approaches after i.v. administration of 2 mg/kg in Wistar rats

Pharmacokinetic Parameters	LAP		LAP sodium salt	
	NCA	2-Comp	NCA	2-Comp
a ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	-	10.0 $\pm$ 4.1	-	11.0 $\pm$ 14.7
b ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	-	8.8 $\pm$ 3.1	-	9.8 $\pm$ 1.9
α (h^{-1})	-	1.76 $\pm$ 1.52	-	8.6 $\pm$ 6.8
β (h^{-1})	-	0.19 $\pm$ 0.03	-	0.20 $\pm$ 0.03
λ (h^{-1})	0.18 $\pm$ 0.04	-	0.30 $\pm$ 0.11	-
$t_{1/2\alpha}$ (h)	-	0.6 $\pm$ 0.4	-	0.19 $\pm$ 0.16
$t_{1/2\beta}$ (h)	-	3.7 $\pm$ 0.5	-	3.5 $\pm$ 0.5
$t_{1/2}$ (h)	4.1 $\pm$ 1.1	-	2.5 $\pm$ 0.8	-
AUC _{0-∞} ($\mu\text{g h/mL}$)	56.1 $\pm$ 20.1	56.4 $\pm$ 21.6	54.5 $\pm$ 26.8	50.8 $\pm$ 11.8
CL _{tot} (L/kg)	0.04 $\pm$ 0.01	0.04 $\pm$ 0.01	0.04 $\pm$ 0.02	0.04 $\pm$ 0.01
Vc (L/kg)	-	0.11 $\pm$ 0.03	-	0.12 $\pm$ 0.06
Vd _{ss} (L/kg)	0.19 $\pm$ 0.03	0.17 $\pm$ 0.03	0.29 $\pm$ 0.17	0.20 $\pm$ 0.04
MRT (h)	5.3 $\pm$ 1.2	-	6.5 $\pm$ 4.1	4.9 $\pm$ 0.8

LAP sodium salt (n =6); LAP (n = 7).